

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

Policy recommendations for national, regional and local stakeholders for the agricultural and delivery sector in Germany.

Policy Brief

Martina Liebsch, Markus Rheindorf, Beatrice Bianca
Salamena, and Bastian Vollmer

March 2026

Funded by the European Union under Grant Number 101094373. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Summary

Within the I-Claim Research in Germany, the general findings of the ethnographic research point to a targeted exploitation of migrant groups who are disadvantaged through certain characteristics (e.g. young age coupled with lack of information and/or living in precarity in Germany or in the country of origin). These concrete mechanisms of targeting and exploiting vulnerable and disadvantaged migrant groups applied in both sectors, namely agriculture and delivery. Notably, the research concludes that most migrants in Germany who take up legal or semi-legal employment hold some form of legal residence permit (international student visa in the case of the delivery sector, EU-Citizens in the case of seasonal workers in the agricultural sector). Moreover, for seasonal workers in agriculture from third countries the access is currently limited to Moldovans and Georgians.¹

These findings show that legal residence status alone does not protect against exploitation; instead, sector-specific structures and recruitment pathways generate vulnerability even among workers with regular permits. The hereafter presented recommendations are meant to counteract these mechanisms and support the access to rights.

Acknowledgements

Thanks go to the persons who were willing to share their personal story and their problems. A special thank you goes to the members of the communities who helped to contact affected people. Finally, we thank the experts who accompanied us through interviews and stakeholder meetings acting like a “sounding board” for our work and enriching it with their questions and suggestions.

Introduction

The groups at the centre of this research, i.e., people with irregular status and precarious living conditions in the agricultural and delivery sectors, occupy a paradoxical position in the sense that they are both highly visible and largely invisible. Delivery riders, for example, are a constant presence in the urban landscape, yet there is limited awareness of their living conditions and little sustained interest in understanding their realities. A similar pattern applies to agricultural workers, many of whom are seasonal migrants. Their essential role in ensuring food security became briefly visible during the COVID-19 pandemic, but public attention to their working and living conditions has once again faded. Moreover, there was a shift in narratives on irregular migration during the electoral campaign and after the last elections in 2025 and thus overlapping with the research period. Irregular migration became an overall topic, implicitly expanding the idea of irregular immigration to, e.g., asylum seekers and conveying the message that irregular migrants are “criminals” and “abusers” of the welfare system. The I-Claim country report on “The Legal and Policy Infrastructure of Irregularity” (Germany) concludes that “[i]t is clear that legal reforms alone are often not enough to improve the day-to-day reality of irregular migrants’ lives. They also need to be implemented in practice and monitored.”² In the document’s conclusion, the authors argue that abolishing a legal reporting requirement on paper does not automatically make life safer for irregularised migrants, especially when

¹ See Federal Employment Agency <https://www.arbeitsagentur.de/unternehmen/fachkraefte-ausland/saisonarbeitskraefte-drittstaaten> and Confederation of German Agricultural and Forestry Employers’ Associations <https://www.glfa.de/saisonarbeitskraefte/> (Last access 17.12.2025)

² Rheindorf, M., Vollmer, M. & Liebsch, M. (2024) The legal and policy infrastructure of irregularity: Germany. ICLAIM. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.111095, p.

institutions continue old practices. They point out that reporting obligations still function as a major obstacle to accessing basic rights, and that the absence of regularisation options leaves many people trapped in irregular status, with harmful consequences both for those affected and for Germany.³

The overarching insight emerging from the research for both sectors is that, in order to substantially improve working and living conditions, steps must be taken to ensure fair wages, secure contracts, access to adequate housing, social protection and effective labour rights enforcement. Specifically, the following recommendations are proposed:

Recommendation # 1:

Taking legislative and law enforcement measures

Recommendation # 2:

Raising awareness, information and training concerning labour rights among migrant workers, employers and authorities

Recommendation # 3:

Providing healthy, safe and inclusive living and working conditions

Recommendation # 4:

Ensuring access to and representation in trade unions and relevant NGOs

Strengthening these areas is crucial not only to safeguarding the dignity, health and fundamental rights of migrant workers, but also to promoting social cohesion and economic sustainability in Germany. Improving conditions in the agricultural and delivery sectors will help reduce exploitation and precarity, stabilise the workforce and ensure the long-term resilience of essential services such as food production and urban logistics.

Methodology

Agriculture

Reaching seasonal workers – the group of people at the heart of our research – was particularly challenging due to the remote and rural location of the areas where migrant workers are employed in the agricultural sector. Moreover, accessing the field proved to be highly challenging due to the widespread caution and reluctance of key stakeholders. Overall, the topic of migrant agricultural labour appeared to be shrouded in a culture of silence and guardedness, making ethnographic engagement particularly difficult. During the ethnographic research, six formal expert interviews were conducted with NGOs, trade unions, a lawyer and other actors involved in the field of agricultural work. The majority of the workers are EU-citizens and consequently have regular residence status; however, they face precarious and exploitative working conditions (Bruzelius and Seeleib-Kaiser, 2023). As they are often unaware of the legal or semi-legal status of their own employment terms, they shy away from speaking with NGOs, which function like trade unions, or with other individuals who might play a role in conducting inspections. The language barrier posed a significant challenge as many workers only speak their mother tongue, with Bulgarian, Romanian and Polish being the most commonly used languages. Hence, the Romanian-speaking community researcher employed to support the data collection was a key figure in building trust with the migrant workers. Nevertheless, suspiciousness was common and some of the migrants refused to talk to us after having listened to the explanation

³ Ibid. p. 33

of the research objective or broke off the interview when inquiries into forms of contract or exploitative issues became very upfront. In all interviews, it became clear that there is an extreme fear of speaking or sharing anything negative about working conditions. This was evident even though we assured interlocutors of complete confidentiality and conducted the interviews away from their workplace. These barriers made effective communication difficult and prevented the researcher from successfully explaining the research objective. In addition, the physically demanding labour often led to exhaustion during breaks, which further limited their availability and willingness to participate in interviews. All interviews with migrant workers were conducted outside a local supermarket frequented by the participants. In total, eighteen individuals were interviewed – three women and fifteen men, all Romanian origin, of which fifteen belonged to Roma communities.⁴

Delivery

The ethnographic research was conducted in the city of Berlin. Half of the interviews with migrant workers took place in person, mostly during their working hours. The other half of the interviews were conducted online via Zoom and, thus, off working hours. The respective circumstances influenced the nature and duration of the interviews. For the interviews conducted during working hours in the street, the length of the interviews depended on their current workload. However, this approach also enabled the formulation of subsequent inquiries concerning clothing, equipment, bicycles, the functionality of the app, the primary point of contact in case of issues, and the way migrant workers spent their breaks. All interviews were conducted in English, which all participants spoke fluently. An Indian community researcher facilitated contact with participants and provided assistance when communication in English proved challenging. The role of gender in establishing contact was found to be significant, with the male community researcher being particularly effective in this regard. Some migrants stated at the end of the interview that they would not have agreed to participate or would not have responded if approached by a female researcher. This is due to patriarchal social structures in the home states of India and differed depending on the cultural and religious background of the interlocutor. The majority of participants, twenty-two in total opted to remain anonymous, with some choosing not to disclose their names, which made it challenging to secure follow-up interviews. Most interviewees consented to having their interviews recorded. A total of six experts were interviewed.⁵

After the ethnographic fieldwork was completed, the results were analysed and common issues/findings for both groups identified, which were the basis for a first rough draft of recommendations. These were presented at the 3rd stakeholder meeting. Participants of the stakeholder meetings were experts, but also persons with an interest in the issue from different perspectives (media, political foundations, counselling centres, academia). Nine persons participated in the 3rd stakeholder meeting, including representatives from the Ministry of Labour, academia, counselling centres, an interest group for agriculture, NGOs and Trade Unions. A participant in the research had promised to come, but then refrained from it, out of fear for negative consequences. After collecting the results of the meeting all invited persons (around 50) were asked to comment on the recommendations. Two comments were received. The first official draft of the recommendations included the suggestions and amendments of the stakeholders and were reviewed by the German I-CLAIM partners. They were also presented and commented during the final policy event. The need to develop a strategy for dissemination and advocacy was stressed.

⁴ For further details see: Salamena, B.B. (2025). Living and Working Conditions of migrant seasonal workers in agriculture in Germany. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/15775486.p.6ff>

⁵ For further details see: Salamena, B.B. (2025). Irregularised migrants in the Delivery Sector (Berlin). I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/15775449.p.6ff>

Main research findings

Gender and household

Concerns of women are largely ignored in male-dominated spaces. Household in terms of familial ties and supportive ties play a crucial role in how migrants organize themselves here and at home. Supportive ties extend outside of the family to other possible circles of support.

In/formal recruitment

Migration status and aspirations coupled with disadvantaged life circumstances promote exploitation by employers.

Insecure and Unsafe Working Conditions

Life factors such as healthcare, job safety, financial security and access to pension rights are entangled with employment. This causes a high dependency.

Emotional burden (physical work and psychological stress) and dependency

The physical hardship of these workplaces (agriculture and delivery) may cause psychological stress, as well as the circumstances back home (e.g. family, friends, politics).

Mechanism of Threat and Silence

Inadequate management structures (threats and silence) cause an atmosphere of fear.

It is not the migration status alone that makes persons vulnerable to precarious living and working conditions, but a set of distinct factors that contribute to it. "The Concept of Vulnerability" ⁶ provides a framework to organise and understand those factors. It explains why workers may have limited ability to refuse exploitative conditions or to report them without risking severe consequences. Moreover, it encourages multidisciplinary and multifaceted interventions. According to this concept four factors interact:

1. Legal factors of vulnerability are the unsecure residence and working conditions, the unclear responsibilities who should address them and limitations in enforcing existing laws.
2. Unequal living conditions among countries, the demand for cheap workforce and goods, the invisibility of the work and the dependency of the workers act as structural factors of vulnerability
3. Individual factors of vulnerability include, among others, the lack of information, the lack of language knowledge, the lack of confidence or lack of emergency funds in case of a complaint/report
4. Finally, factors of social vulnerability are the lack of safe spaces and support networks, isolation, or being in relations of power imbalance. These factors cannot be clearly separated from one another. However, they give orientation in which areas support (services) may be needed.

⁶ Cyrus, Norbert: Soziale Unterstützung für Betroffene extremer Arbeitsausbeutung - ein neues Feld Sozialer Arbeit? In: Migration und Soziale Arbeit 34 (4): 311-317

Each vulnerability dimension corresponds to a policy domain:

- legal vulnerability → regularisation and rights information
- structural vulnerability → labour inspections and wage protections
- individual vulnerability → outreach, counselling and interpretation
- social vulnerability → safe spaces, accommodation standards and self-organisation.

To effectively mitigate these vulnerabilities, they must be addressed through their corresponding policy domains and institutional authorities. Legal vulnerabilities require measures such as regularisation pathways and access to rights-based information; structural vulnerabilities call for strengthened labour inspections and wage protections; individual vulnerabilities must be tackled through outreach initiatives, counselling services, language courses and interpretation support; and social vulnerabilities necessitate the provision of safe spaces, adequate accommodation standards and support for workers' self-organisation.

Policy recommendations

RECOMMENDATION #1:

Legislative and law enforcement measures

It is important to codify the obligation on the part of employers in a law or another regulation to inform their employees about labour rights, occupational health and safety, if needed supported by language mediators or at minimum where they can find support and information. As of January 2026, such an obligation exists for employers who employ third country nationals. It is enshrined in the National Action Plan against labour exploitation and forced labour (NAP A/Z)⁷.

The National Action Plan against labour exploitation and forced labour of the Federal government contains eighty-three measures in the areas of (1) recruitment, (2) enforcement of the rights of workers, (3) working conditions, health and safety in the workplace and governmental control and (4) corporate responsibility. The recommendations in this policy brief intend to support, reinforce and contribute to the NAP A/Z.

In both the agricultural and delivery sectors, workers are frequently recruited through informal or irregular intermediaries, including employers, subcontractors, co-workers and acquaintances. These intermediaries often provide inaccurate or incomplete information about wages, hours, accommodation, or fees, and may charge workers for recruitment—creating debt, dependency and heightened vulnerability.

To address this, German authorities should introduce mandatory licensing for all recruitment agents operating in Germany in these sectors and require regular audits of their activities. In case of recruitment in the country of origin of the worker, the German government should seek transnational cooperation to indicate problems related to informal and irregular recruitment. Irregular or deceptive recruitment should be sanctioned, including administrative fines and labour-law penalties. National Authorities should

⁷ <https://www.bmas.de/DE/Service/Presse/Meldungen/2025/nationaler-aktionsplan-gegen-arbeitsausbeutung-und-zwangsarbeit-beschlossen.html> (last access 18.02.2026)

establish a central monitoring system to verify compliance, aligned with the ILO General principles and operational guidelines for fair recruitment.⁸ These steps also respond to existing recommendations from German civil society⁹, including the call to ratify ILO Convention 181 on Private Employment Agencies, thereby closing key regulatory gaps in agricultural and platform-based recruitment chains.¹⁰

Foreign students from third countries are in need to work to finance their living while studying abroad as living costs prove to be more expensive as expected. According to existing regulations they are allowed to work 20 h (140 full days per year) per week. Many of them choose to work in the delivery sector because of the easy accessibility (via platform) and flexibility. It seems that the working hours they are allowed to work are not sufficient to cover their needs, also because they are paid by order and often do not receive the minimum wage. They can extend their working hours upon permission by the immigration authorities, which they might not know or avoid. It is key that this sector is controlled by the respective authorities and that the status of the worker as worker or self-employed is clarified as depending on the status they have access to key labour rights, such as clear working hours, social protection, holidays etc. The forthcoming transposition of Directive (EU) 2024/2831 on improving working conditions in platform work is essential, including the presumption of employment, algorithmic transparency obligations, strengthened data rights and limitations on automated decision-making affecting the precarious working conditions as documented in this research. Immigration authorities should be required to inform student workers proactively about the possibility of extending permissible working hours and to provide multilingual guidance. Platforms must be legally required to classify workers correctly and must not 'externalise' employer responsibilities by falsely designating them as self-employed.

A monitoring body should investigate whether laws and measures have side-effects that undermine the labour rights of the concerned groups.

RECOMMENDATION #2:

Raising awareness, information and training concerning labour rights among migrant workers, employers and authorities

One of the key steps towards improving conditions for seasonal and delivery workers is establishing clear contact points that inform and raise awareness concerning labour rights. In the agricultural sector, contact points for farmers to obtain relevant information are crucial. These points of contact should provide guidance on the challenges associated with employing seasonal workers, particularly addressing issues such as conflicts among diverse groups of workers and ensuring their labour rights are upheld.

⁸ https://www.ilo.org/sites/default/files/wcmsps/groups/public/%40oed_protect/%40protrav/%40migrant/documents/publication/wcms_536755.pdf (last access 26.02.2026)

⁹ The Federal Government should encourage all public and private recruitment (last access 26.11.25) agencies to follow the ILO "General principles and operational guidelines for fair recruitment and definition of recruitment fees and related costs." It should ratify and implement the ILO Convention No. 181 (Private Employment Agencies Convention, 1997) and ensure licensing and monitoring of recruitment agencies by the authorities. In case of governmental recruitment initiatives (e.g., in the care sector), recruitment must follow the fair recruitment standards and take place only through certified agencies. The Government should put in place effective complaints mechanisms which include the possibility of individual claims against fraudulent recruiters as well as international reporting on fraudulent recruitment, Report of German Civil Society Organisations for the International Migration Review Forum (IMRF) taking place on 17 – 20 May 2022, Implementation of the Global Compact on Migration, Priority Recommendations, GCM objective 6, p. 4., https://www.der-paritaetische.de/fileadmin/user_upload/2022_02_Report_German_CS_O_IMRF_final_Priority_Recommendations_Discussion_Paper.pdf (last access 26.02.2026)

¹⁰ https://normlex.ilo.org/dyn/nrmlx_en/f?p=NORMLEXPUB:12100:0::NO::P12100_INSTRUMENT_ID:312326 (Last access 26.02.2026)

Ensuring that migrant workers have easy access to multilingual information in digital and printed format about the German labour market and labour rights is also essential. This information should be made readily available, e.g., in the reception facilities managed by the employer, workspaces and meeting points, through notices or apps. The information sharing should be facilitated by employers. Developing and disseminating appropriate information would be a multilevel task, both by national and federal stakeholder, like national and local authorities, trade unions in cooperation with those close to experience of the worker, like worker advisory centres, labour inspectorates and migrant organisations. Providing clear information helps prevent workers from falling into exploitative structures that offer quick but substandard employment opportunities, which is a significant concern in both sectors. It ensures that all workers, regardless of their language skills, have access to the information they need to protect themselves and assert their rights.

A promising example that emerged from the 3rd stakeholder meeting and could help in disseminating information is the development of a mobile application, such as an “Agri Worker App 2.0.”¹¹ The Ministry of Labour, in cooperation with unions, worker advisory centres and migrant organisations, should develop and maintain an ‘Agri Worker App 2.0’ that includes: (1) a working-hours logbook compliant with German labour law; (2) multilingual rights and health care information; and (3) an anonymised complaint function connected to advisory centres. A similar app could be created for the delivery sector.

In addition to apps, social media can play a role in spreading awareness about the work and challenges faced by delivery riders. A targeted digital outreach strategy (e.g. short videos in workers’ languages distributed through TikTok, YouTube, Instagram) should be implemented to reach younger migrant workers in the delivery sectors who rely primarily on mobile platforms for information and networking. For instance, a testimony could share scenes from a rider’s daily life, providing practical guidance on how to manage common issues, along with information on workers’ rights. Although some documentaries exist on this topic, they do not always reach the people who need the information most¹².

Moreover, it is important to offer seminars on labour rights, free of charge and during working hours, especially tailored for seasonal workers and delivery workers. The time spent in the seminar should be compensated like working hours. These seminars could be organized by advisory centres that can directly engage with workers, raising awareness and providing guidance on their legal rights. By doing so, workers will be better equipped to navigate potential challenges in the workplace and victims of exploitation could be identified.

Finally, training for police officers is crucial in managing conflicts that may arise among diverse groups in both the agricultural and delivery sectors. This training would help law enforcement understand how to de-escalate situations effectively while preventing discriminatory behaviour, whether within the conflict groups or towards the authorities themselves. Since these sectors often involve private property or public spaces, officers need specific knowledge to handle these disputes with sensitivity and respect for workers’ rights.

¹¹ Here an example from Austria: <https://noe.landarbeiterkammer.at/aktuelles/berichte/news/agri-worker-app-ist-online> (last access 18.02.2026)

¹² Example: <https://www.3sat.de/gesellschaft/makro/wirtschaftsdokumentation-die-harte-welt-der-lieferdienste-100.html> (last access 04.12.25)

RECOMMENDATION #3:**Providing a healthy, safe and inclusive living and working environment**

Domestic safety and privacy are essential basic needs that must be considered in connection with accommodation provided by the employer, especially in the agricultural sector. Unfortunately, there are accommodations that do not cater for these needs. The accommodation is unsafe as it may be offered in run-down or unsuitable buildings (barns, warehouses) and with poor sanitation facilities. Community spaces may be lacking as well as private spaces for individuals or families. Accommodation must adhere to the standards established under the Arbeitsschutzkontrollgesetz (Occupational Safety and Health Act)¹³, including minimum space per person, functioning sanitation, heating and privacy provisions. Regular inspections should be mandatory for employers providing on-site housing.

In the food delivery sector, the research has shown that the drivers meet in front of the premises of the companies where they charge the ordered goods or in informal meeting points, where the paths of many of them cross. Therefore it is similarly imperative to provide warm retreat areas that give drivers an opportunity to network and a place to rest and access sanitary services. Particularly in view of the digital structures that characterize this sector, communication and exchange are essential for drivers to support each other.

In general, safe spaces for all groups concerned are important, especially for women and children. In the delivery sector, there is still a need to include female perspectives on public space in relation to safety due to night-time driving. Harassment or violence may occur when delivering goods at the house doors or also in accommodations without safe, private spaces for women.¹⁴

Moreover, employers should be legally obliged to provide workers with all necessary work equipment and to bear the costs of its maintenance. This includes, for platform workers, the provision of essential tools such as smartphones and bicycles, and for agricultural workers, adequate protective work clothing, including gloves, footwear and trousers.

It is also crucial to enable participation and solidarity in the working environment by promoting, supporting and allowing for “integration measures” that foster community (e.g., common room with canteen with the possibility to offer leisure activities such as movie nights in the native language) among the workers. In the agricultural sector some employers offer such measures, even if not funded.¹⁵

Finally, the self-organization of foreign workers must be allowed, promoted, supported and respected by employers and their representatives as well as by authorities.

¹³ <https://www.bmas.de/DE/Service/Gesetze-und-Gesetzesvorhaben/arbeitsschutzkontrollgesetz.html>: The law aims to establish orderly and safe working conditions in the meat industry. In addition, it establishes uniform nationwide rules for the inspection of businesses and the accommodation of employees in other industries as well. (last access 17.12.2025)

¹⁴ The representative of the Confederation of German Agricultural and Forestry Employers' Associations in a written statement for the 3. stakeholder meeting wrote: “The amount of violence against women remains unclear.”

¹⁵ Ibid.

RECOMMENDATION #4:**Access to and representation in trade unions and relevant NGOs**

Given the unfamiliarity of many of the workers in these sectors with national labour and occupational safety laws it is imperative that they have access to unions or other organisations competent in providing support and represent their concerns vis á vis the employers. Employers should be obliged to grant unions and recognised NGOs regular access to work sites at designated times, including in agricultural settings where access is restricted due to private property rules.

Trade unions and NGOs that are committed to work on the issue of labour exploitation and occupational safety for migrants must be more actively involved in institutionalized processes that ensure occupational safety in the interests of employees. They should also have legally secured access to the workplace for providing counselling to the workers.

In the field of agriculture, farms and land are private property and this must be respected. However, farmers should be obliged to allow for regular times when unions and associations have access to the land to inform workers.

Workers, also those in irregular work, should be able to claim their rights without putting the worker at risk of losing its job. For this purpose, accessible places for filing complaints should be made available.

Complaints filed by workers, regardless of residence status, must not be shared with immigration enforcement. Labour-law enforcement and migration enforcement must remain institutionally separated. A national multilingual hotline and an anonymous online reporting platform operated by either the Ministry of Labour or an independent ombudsperson should be established.

Overview of the recommendations sorted according to the concept of vulnerability (see table in the annex)

For further reference: I-Claim country reports – Germany[The Legal and Policy Infrastructure of Irregularity: Germany](#)

Markus Rheindorf, Bastian Vollmer, Martina Liebsch

Catholic University of Applied Sciences in Mainz and Catholic Forum “Living in Illegality”

March 2024

[Discourses about irregularised migrants in German](#)

Markus Rheindorf and Bastian Vollmer

Catholic University of Applied Sciences in Mainz

This report presents key findings and conclusions from a large-scale corpus analysis of text addressing irregularised migrants and migration in the domains of media, politics, and civil society.

February 2025

[Living and Working Conditions of migrant seasonal workers in agriculture in Germany](#)

Beatrice Bianca Salamena

Catholic University of Applied Sciences in Mainz

June 2025

This report presents the overview of the key findings on the working conditions of migrant seasonal workers in the agricultural sector in Germany.

[Irregularised migrants in the Delivery Sector \(Berlin\)](#)

Beatrice Bianca Salamena

Catholic University of Applied Sciences in Mainz

The present report offers a synopsis of the principal findings of WP5 within the broader I-CLAIM Project, with a particular focus on the working conditions of migrants in the food delivery sector in Berlin.

June 2025

[Moving beyond securitisation and deservingness: Convergence between political and media discourses about 'irregular migrants' in Germany](#)

Markus Rheindorf and Bastian Vollmer

Catholic University of Applied Sciences in Mainz

This article presents findings from a large-scale discourse analysis that examines how 'irregular migration' and the figure of the 'irregular migrant' are constructed across political and media discourse.

2025

Annexes

A Overview of the Recommendations sorted according to the concept of vulnerability

Vulnerability	Recommendation	Details	Actors
Legal vulnerability	<i>Legislative and law enforcement measures</i>	Mandatory information of workers about labour rights, occupational health and safety	Employers
		Mandatory licensing for recruitment agents operating in Germany	German government
		Sanction deceptive recruitment	German government
		Transnational cooperation for recruitment agents operating in other countries	German government
		Establish a monitoring system to verify compliance with ILO General principles	German government
		Control the delivery sector and clarify status of workers incl. working hours, social protection and holidays	German government
		Establish a monitoring body which verifies if laws have side-effects that undermine the labour rights of the concerned groups	German government
Structural vulnerability	<i>Raising awareness, information and training concerning labour rights among migrant workers, employers and authorities</i>	Establish contact points informing about labour rights and challenges associated with employing seasonal workers for employers in the Agri sector	Farmer association Police/customs
		Ensure easy access to multilingual, digital and printed information in spaces where workers move; explore the development of an App for the respective sectors or a digital strategy incl. social media (most of the riders are young people)	National and regional authorities, trade unions, advisory centres
		Offer seminars free of charge for workers during remunerated working hours	Advisory centres, trade unions
		Training for police officers in managing conflicts among diverse groups in both sectors	Police at regional level

Individual vulnerability	<i>Providing a healthy, safe and inclusive living and working environment</i>	Ensure accommodation provided for the workers adheres to the Arbeitsschutzkontrollgesetz (Occupational Safety and Health ACT) (ArbSchKG)	Customs (labour inspections)
		Ensure that drivers in the platform economy have retreat and networking areas and access to sanitary services	Customs (labour inspections)
		Ensure the existence of safe, private spaces, especially for women and children	Employers, customs
		Take measures to protect women from harassment in both sectors	Employers, trade unions, customs
		Mandatory provision of work equipment free of charge and bearing the costs for its maintenance	Legislator, employer
		Encourage the provision for “integration” and socialising measures that foster community	Employer
		Allow, promote, support and respect self-organisation of foreign workers	National and regional authorities, employers, trade unions
Social vulnerability	<i>Access to and representation in trade unions and relevant NGOs</i>	Facilitate access of the workers to unions or NGOs which provide support	Trade unions, NGOs
		Grant unions and NGOs the right to access work sites	Legislator, Employers
		Ensure involvement of unions, NGOs and other stakeholder to institutionalized processes that ensure occupational safety of the workers	Competent authorities
		Ensure access to justice, e.g. claiming wages without risk of losing jobs in case of irregular workers, at minimum places where to file complaints; labour-law enforcement and migration enforcement must be institutionally separated (firewall)	Legislator
		Establish a national multilingual hotline and an anonymous online reporting system to file complaints	Ministry of Labour/independent ombudsperson

B Best practice examples

Best practice examples must be given greater prominence so that established and successful models can be used as a guidance for others to emulate. Highlighting these examples demonstrates that improved working conditions are not only possible but already realised in parts of Germany, providing models for scalable and cost-effective reform.

Some examples are:

Arbeit und Leben:

<https://www.berlin.arbeitundleben.de/migration-und-gute-arbeit/>

“Good and decent work for all! The rights of migrants and mobile workers in the German labour market are particularly frequently violated: illegal dismissals, unpaid wages, inadequate occupational safety, and embezzled working hours. We inform migrant workers in many languages about their rights and support them in enforcing them. Together with our networks at regional, national, and international level, we want to change social structures so that violations of rights, from labour exploitation to forced labour and human trafficking, no longer have a place. To this end, we work closely with trade unions, civil society organizations, and government agencies in Germany and Europe.” (Translated with DeepL)

Faire Integration:

<https://www.faire-integration.de/en/topic/2.welcome.html>

Fair Integration advice centres

Fair Integration is a counselling service in Germany for refugees and migrants from third countries (outside the EU) on social and labour law issues. The counselling service is available in all federal states and is provided by various organisations. Counselling is offered free of charge, anonymously and in various languages of origin. Counselling topics include labour and social law issues that are directly related to the employment relationship, such as working hours, dismissal, temporary work and many more. Available in seven languages apart from German.

Platform for the recruitment of seasonal workers in agriculture:

<http://www.saisonarbeit-in-deutschland.de/>

Farmers can present their farm and workplace, and workers can look for a seasonal job (in Polish, Rumanian and Bulgarian). This website will be relaunched in 2026. It will be more user friendly, so that those who use it, know if they are allowed to come to Germany and can directly contact the employer. The intention is to avoid that workers must pay for recruiters or intermediaries. The website will be translated in different languages apart from German.

Thanks to the **German Supply Chain Act**¹⁶ investigations against a polish company in the delivery sector were possible. Important in this case was the organisations of the workers (Strike in Gräfenhausen) and the cooperation with Trade Unions and other relevant stakeholder. The employer was responsible for inhumane working conditions and outstanding wage payments.¹⁷

¹⁶ https://www.bmas.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/Publikationen/a432e-act-on-corporate-due-diligence-obligations-in-supply-chains.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=5 (last access 05.12.2025)

¹⁷ <https://fachanwaelte-strafrecht-potsdamer-platz.de/de/news/compliance/629-erste-lksg-ermittlungen-gegen-deutsche-unternehmen>

i-CLAIM Consortium

Utrecht
University

UNIVERSITY OF
BIRMINGHAM

Ca' Foscari
University
of Venice

Department of Philosophy
and Cultural Heritage

UNIVERSITY
OF WARSAW

HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO
HELSINGFORS UNIVERSITET
UNIVERSITY OF HELSINKI

Katholische
Hochschule Mainz
Catholic University
of Applied Sciences

TOGETHER FOR
JUSTICE & EQUALITY
THE JOINT COUNCIL
for THE WELFARE
OF IMMIGRANTS

act:ionaid
— REALIZZA IL CAMBIAMENTO —

Centrala

ASSOCIATION
FOR LEGAL
INTERVENTION

CONFEDERATION
SYNDICAT
EUROPÉEN
TRADE UNION

Deaconess
Foundation

KATHOLISCHES
FORUM

LEBEN IN DER
LEGALITÄT

Contact info

icclaim@uu.nl

For press inquiries:

I-CLAIM Communications Manager

miriam.mir@ceps.eu

Follow us

www.i-claim.eu

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe